

NORMAL AND PATHOLOGICAL PHYSIOLOGY

INVESTIGATION OF THIOL/DISULFIDE HOMEOSTASIS AS AN OXIDATIVE STRESS PATHWAY IN DEVELOPMENTAL DYSPLASIA OF THE HIP

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Abstract

Objectives: The present study sought to investigate the role of thiol–disulfide homeostasis (TDH) acting as a specific biochemical pathway of oxidative stress in the etiology of Developmental Dysplasia of the Hip (DDH).

Study Design: Randomised control trial.

Place and Duration of the Study: Department of Orthopedics and Traumatology, Harran University Faculty of Medicine, Şanlıurfa, Türkiye. From April 2020 to May 2023.

Methodology: Venous blood samples were collected from children with DDH and the control group. Participants were assessed for oxidative stress status including TDH and systemic oxidative stress parameters. Clinical outcomes were assessed using Tönnis grading and acetabular index measurements.

Results: After treatment, clinical scores in patients improved significantly than the pretreatment scores. In DDH patients, systemic oxidative parameters were significantly higher than in the control group, while TDH values did not show a statistical difference. TDH metabolism in the patient group showed a significant improvement after treatment.

Discussion: This is the first study to investigate the potential role of dynamic TDH metabolism in DDH. There is no difference in TDH parameters between patients before treatment and the control group. However, TDH improved significantly in DDH patients after treatment. This can be attributed to the decrease in overall oxidative stress.

Keywords: developmental dysplasia of the hip, thiol-disulfide, oxidative stress.

Introduction

The hip joint is stabilized by the acetabulum, joint capsule, and surrounding connective tissues. During embryogenesis normal hip joint development may be disrupted by various precipitating factors such as ligamentous laxity, breech presentation, and postnatal posture under the influence of hormonal and genetic factors. Based on this etiology that also includes postnatal factors, Davies and Walker coined the term “Developmental Dysplasia of the Hip (DDH)” in 1984. This term has expanded the spectrum of the disease to cover acetabular dysplasia, subluxation, and dislocation resulting from capsular laxity and abnormal development of the hip.¹

Energy production is achieved by oxidative phosphorylation reactions at the cellular level, resulting in endogenous formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). However, ROS may also result from exposure to exogenous conditions such as aging, infection, xenobiotics, ischemia-reperfusion injury, high oxygen pres-

sure, and radiation.² ROS reportedly can damage biological structures and cause tissue damage, but these effects can be counterbalanced by antioxidant defense systems. Under physiological conditions, ROS and antioxidants are in equilibrium.³ The condition when this balance shifts in favor of ROS is called “oxidative stress”. Oxidative stress has been shown to trigger the etiopathogenesis of numerous diseases.⁴

Thiol-based antioxidant compounds containing sulfhydryl (-SH) groups (albumin, cysteine, γ -glutamyl cysteine, cysteinyl glycine, glutathione, and homocysteine) act as a defense mechanism against oxidative stress by reducing oxygen in ROS and oxidizing themselves.⁵ This leads to covalent bonds of disulfide-based (-S-S) compounds between ROS and oxidized thiol groups. Such a decrease in the amount of native thiol- (NT) and total thiol- (TT) based compounds and increase in the amount of disulfide- (DS) based compounds indicate oxidative stress. Conversely, an increase in NT and TT indicates reduced oxidative stress. This state is called thiol–disulfide homeostasis (TDH).

Ability of DS-based compounds to be reduced back to thiol-based compounds via reversible reactions allows the maintenance of TDH. Studies have implicated dysregulated TDH in the pathogenesis of numerous diseases such as chronic renal failure, liver diseases, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, cancer, AIDS, rheumatoid arthritis, and neurodegenerative diseases.⁴

The relationship between oxidative stress and DDH has already been demonstrated.⁶ Based on the hypothesis that normal or abnormal results of TDH, as an oxidative stress mechanism, can provide useful information about patients with DDH, this study sought to investigate the relationship between DDH and dynamic TDH.

Methodology

In this prospective study, patients who were diagnosed with and treated for DDH were assessed between April 2020 and May 2023 at Harran University Faculty of Medicine, Department of Orthopedics and Traumatology. The study received local ethics committee approval (decision no: HRU/20.07.16-16987). The families of all participants were informed about the study

procedure and provided written informed consent. The study was conducted in accordance with the World Medical Association's Declaration of Helsinki and included children aged 1.5–60 months who were diagnosed with primary DDH based on standardized clinical criteria and radiographic examinations and had no comorbidities. Patients with secondary diseases and five patients diagnosed with cerebral palsy during follow-up were excluded, and two patients were could not be followed up.

The study involved the analysis and comparison of oxidative stress values in 95 patients with DDH (Group 1) at initial presentation and at the end of the follow-up period and those of 98 healthy controls (Group 2). Patients and controls had no significant difference in terms of age ($p < 0.05$). Patients were followed up for 2–23 months. Group I consisted of 95 patients (18 males and 77 females), age range: 1.5–60 months (10.32 ± 8.95), and Group II consisted of 98 healthy controls (32 males and 66 females), age range: 2–28 months (11.82 ± 4.79). The demographic characteristics of the participants are presented in Table-1.

Table-1

Demographic characteristics of controls and patients

Demographics	Patients	Controls	P-value
Number of patients (n)	95	98	
Age (month) (mean \pm SD)	10.32 ± 8.95	11.82 ± 4.79	0.146
Sex			
Female (n, %)	77 (81.05%)	66 (67.3%)	*0.024
Male (n, %)	18 (18.95%)	32 (32.7%)	
*Significant at $p < 0.05$; Wilcoxon test; SD, standard deviation; n, number of patients			

Patients with DDH were assessed for Tönnis grading and acetabular index (AI) values immediately after the diagnosis, and venous blood was collected from them to assess oxidative stress values. When the Tönnis clinical score of the patients reached grade 1 during follow-up, venous blood was drawn a second time. Thus, the length of follow-up varied between 2 months and 23 months. For patients with bilateral DDH, a grade of 1 on one side was considered sufficient and assessments were made based on that side.

Serum oxidative stress was assessed using parameters native thiol (NT), total thiol (TT), disulfide (DS), NT/TT ratio, DS/NT ratio, and DS/TT ratio and total antioxidant status (TAS), total oxidant status (TOS), and oxidative stress index (OSI). Diagnosis, follow-up, and interventions were performed by the same orthopedist (Baki Volkan Çetin, MD). Patients received different procedures including follow-up only (9.5%), Pavlik harness (30.5%), closed reduction (40.0%), and open reduction (7.4%). Closed reduction was used when Pavlik harness therapy failed (6.3%), and open reduction was used when closed reduction failed (6.3%). All surgical procedures were followed by the application of a pelvipedal cast.

Venous blood was collected from the antecubital veins of patients with DDH and healthy controls after 8 h of fasting, and samples were placed into blood collection tubes. The blood samples were centrifuged at $1500 \times g$ for 10 min for the separation of cells. The separated serum samples were transferred into sterile Eppendorf tubes and stored at $-86 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Serum TDH parameters

were analyzed using an automated measurement technique developed by Erel and Neselioğlu.⁷ Serum NT and TT levels were determined spectrophotometrically using a Varioskan Lux Multimode microplate reader (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). DS levels were obtained by calculating half of the difference between NT and TT content. Other calculated parameters included oxidized thiol ratio (DS/TT), reduced thiol ratio (NT/TT), and thiol oxidation–reduction (DS/NT) ratio. NT, TT, and DS levels were expressed in $\mu\text{mol/L}$. Serum oxidative stress parameters, including TAS and TOS, were examined based on an automated measurement technique developed by Erel.⁸ Serum TAS and TOS levels were determined spectrophotometrically using a Varioskan Lux Multimode microplate reader (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). Calculation of OSI, an important indicator of oxidative stress, started with the calculation of TOS and TAS units. OSI was calculated according to the following formula:⁹

$$\text{OSI (arbitrary unit)} = \frac{\text{TOS } (\mu\text{mol H}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ equivalent/L})}{\text{TAS } (\mu\text{mol Trolox equivalent/L})} \times 100.$$

Statistical methods

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 25.0. Data sets were assessed for normality of distribution using Shapiro–Wilk test, which helped determine the appropriate statistical techniques for further processing. Normally distributed continuous variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation, whereas those that were non-normally distributed were described using median and interquartile range. Categorical variables were expressed as

number (n) and percentage (%). For comparing two independent samples, the independent samples t-test was used for normally distributed data and Mann–Whitney U test for non-normally distributed data. Data within groups were analyzed using the dependent samples t-test or Wilcoxon signed-rank test depending on distribution. Relationships between continuous variables were analyzed using Pearson's correlation coefficient, and categorical data were analyzed using Pearson's chi-

square test. The results were analyzed at 95% confidence interval, and a p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Post-treatment Tönnis scores and AI measurements in the patient group were observed significant improvement than their pretreatment values ($p < 0.001$) (Table-2).

Table-2

Tönnis and acetabular index scores before treatment and after treatment

Scoring	Pretreatment	Post-treatment	P-value
Tönnis			
Right hip (n=79)	2.07 ± 0.75	1.15 ± 0.51	<0.001*
Left hip (n=78)	2.03 ± 0.78	1.11 ± 0.45	<0.001*
Acetabular index			
Right hip (n=79)	34.60 ± 6.48	26.49 ± 5.42	<0.001*
Left hip (n=78)	34.43 ± 6.49	25.83 ± 5.43	<0.001*

*Significant at $p < 0.05$; nonparametric test (Wilcoxon signed-rank test); n, number of hips

In the patient group, statistically significant improvement of post-treatment values of NT, TT, compared to pretreatment (p value 0.003; 0.026 respectively). Compared with the values in the control group, patients' pretreatment NT, TT, and DS values were lower and NT/TT ratio was higher. After treatment, however, patients had higher NT and TT values and lower DS values compared with the values in the control group.

While pretreatment TOS and OSI were significantly higher than post treatment (p value 0.001; 0.003, respectively), TAS value was lower. Compared to the control group, the TOS values of the patient group pretreatment were significantly higher ($p=0.015$), while the OSI value was higher and the TAS was lower. After the treatment, while a significant improvement was achieved in TOS and OSI values compared to the control group (p value 0.001; 0.018, respectively), TAS values were also similar to the control group (Table-3).

Table-3

Analysis of oxidative stress parameters in controls and patients

	Pretreatment	Post-treatment	Controls	P1	P2	P3
NT (µmol/L)	485.01 (122.96)	515.75 (112.71)	491.84 (145.16)	0.170	0.003*	0.189
TT (µmol/L)	686.40 (281.91)	743.60 (379.97)	731.75 (242.69)	0.432	0.026*	0.068
DS (µmol/L)	104.24 (103.81)	113.79 (162.36)	121.39 (98.53)	0.541	0.340	0.105
DS/TT (%)	15.94 (7.83)	14.93 (11.82)	16.21 (7.99)	0.314	0.863	0.356
NT/TT (%)	68.12 (15.64)	70.15 (23.64)	67.56 (15.99)	0.312	0.862	0.353
DS/NT (%)	23.40 (17.59)	21.28 (27.11)	24.00 (17.09)	0.312	0.926	0.355
TAS (mmol Trolox equiv./l)	0.66 (0.31)	0.68 (0.33)	0.71 (0.44)	0.667	0.966	0.761
TOS (µmol H ₂ O ₂ equiv./l)	11.50 (5.61)	9.19 (5.80)	11.09 (5.94)	0.015*	< 0.001*	0.001*
OSI (arbitrary unit)	1.84 (1.23)	1.43 (1.01)	1.77 (1.78)	0.396	0.003*	0.018*

*Significant at $p < 0.05$; Wilcoxon test; intragroup comparisons were made via Wilcoxon test, and intergroup comparisons were made via Mann–Whitney U test. Median [25%–75%].

P1, P-value of the comparison between patients before treatment and controls; P2, P-value of the comparison between preoperative and postoperative scores in patients; and P3, P-value of the comparison between patients after treatment and controls.

NT (µmol/L), native thiol; TT (µmol/L), total thiol; DS (µmol/L), disulfide; DS/TT (%), disulfide/total thiol (oxidized thiol); NT/TT (%), native thiol/total thiol (reduced thiol); DS/NT (%), disulfide/native thiol (thiol oxidation/reduction); TAS (mmol Trolox equiv./l), total antioxidant status; TOS (µmol H₂O₂ equiv./l), total oxidant status; OSI (arbitrary unit), oxidative stress index

Patients with more severe disease according to the Tönnis grading system before treatment had higher NT and TT values (NT: $r = 0.252$, $p = 0.014$; TT: $r = 0.260$; $p = 0.001$).

The relationship between the applied treatment method and TDH parameters was examined. There was no correlation between the type of treatment and TDH parameters.

Discussion

Although it is not fully understood which factors contribute to the etiology of DDH, a number of predisposing factors are known to be involved. The present study was prompted by the idea that increased body oxidative stress may be a precipitating factor in DDH. Departing from this hypothesis, the study sought to investigate the relationship between DDH and oxidative stress parameters of TDH. Thus, patients with DDH and healthy controls were compared in terms of systemic oxidative stress parameters and TDH. We also compared pretreatment and post-treatment levels of these parameters in patients. Although DDH has been previously investigated in relation to oxidative stress, to our knowledge, no study has yet investigated the relationship between TDH with DDH.^{6,10,11} This study is the first study to investigate the contribution of TDH to the etiology of DDH. The potential implications of this new knowledge are worth being considered for both screening and treatment strategies.

Dynamic TDH status is critical in antioxidant protection mechanisms. Yazar et al. reported that free oxygen radicals can disrupt dynamic TDH and cause oxidative stress.¹² Further, TDH dysregulation has been implicated in increased oxidative stress in several diseases such as hypertension, atopic dermatitis, bipolar disorder, rotator cuff tears, acute pancreatitis, breast cancer, fibromyalgia.¹²⁻¹⁹ In the present study, Our results suggest that free oxygen radicals may be causing oxidative stress not through TDH but via another antioxidant pathway.

All the patients included in this study achieved a satisfactory change in their clinical Tönnis and AI scores after treatment compared with pretreatment values ($p < 0.001$). These significant results suggest that the treatment delivered for each patient with DDH was clinically appropriate and correct. Comparison of the post-treatment levels with the pretreatment results in terms of oxidative biochemical parameters showed a statistically significant increase in NT and TT levels ($p = 0.003$ and $p = 0.026$, respectively). This result demonstrated that TDH improved positively with treatment. Considering that it is challenging to perform a high-quality physical examination on patients with DDH during follow-up checks because of the pelvipedal cast or orthopedic appliances and, positive biochemical NT and TT results may provide a useful guidance for the surgeon. Thus, recording NT and TT values during each visit can provide additional information for facilitating follow-up.

This study showed no correlation between any of the six treatment modalities that were used in patients with DDH and that resulted in clinical and radiologic improvement compared to the pretreatment period and

TDH. This could mean that it is not the treatment modality but achieving Tönnis grade 1 that allows a reduction in oxidative stress.

Although previous studies have reported higher oxidative stress values in patients with DDH compared with healthy children, to our knowledge, no study has yet investigated TDH levels in these patients. The present study compared TDH levels in patients with DDH with those in healthy children. Although there was a significant improvement in NT and TT values in DDH patients with treatment, they did not differ significantly from the control group. For oxidative stress parameters, significant improvement was achieved, especially in TOS and OSI, when compared to the control group before and after treatment. In 2017, Altay et al. reported that oxidative stress parameters in patients with DDH had a statistically negative relationship but noted that the origin of this causality was unclear.⁶ Levels of NT, TT, and DS as well as DS/TT and DS/NT ratios in patients with DDH were lower than the control group. Thus, TDH, as part of oxidative stress metabolism, does not have a direct causal link to the development of DDH. We reviewed the literature for similar abnormal TDH results and found that Balta et al. attributed all these decreased levels to the conversion of DS to S-nitrosothiol, sulfenic acid, sulfinic acid, and sulfonic acid.²⁰ However, this hypothesis needs to be supported by detailed studies examining reversible and irreversible reactions including S-nitrosothiol, sulfenate, sulfinate, and sulfonate. Similarly, Ducrocq et al. noted that thiols can also promote oxidative stress through nitrosative stress by reacting with nitric oxide (NO) to form nitrosothiols.²¹ This evidence shows that the decrease in NT and TT, as well as the lack of increase in DS, may represent nitrosative stress rather than TDH-induced oxidative stress in DDH.

In patients with DDH, post-treatment NT and TT values were higher and DS values were lower than those in healthy children. Low DS values in the presence of systemic oxidative stress was an unexpected result and prompted us to search for similar reports in the literature. In one of those studies, Fidan et al. investigated TDH levels in fibromyalgia and found similar unexpected results.¹⁹ According to the authors, this was linked to proliferative changes, explaining the higher NT and lower DS levels. Fass found similar abnormal change in patients with angina pectoris and concluded that low DS levels may be caused by the protective power of extracellular cysteine pairs in DSs, which protect reactive thiol groups and support protein stability and functioning.²² Uysal et al. reported the presence of oxidative stress and decreased DS levels in atopic dermatitis.¹⁵ They suggested that the decreased DS level may be caused by the rebound phenomenon that works to maintain the protective effect by facilitating the neutralization of the oxidative state. We suggest that the reason why DS values are low despite the presence of systemic oxidative stress is due to oxidative stress that is not caused by TDH. That may be interpreted that oxidative stress is attempted to be corrected by other antioxidant pathways that are not caused by TDH.

Patients with more severe disease before treatment according to the Tönnis grading system had higher NT

and TT values. NT and TT increase as the severity of the disease increases. Based on these results, it appears that as DDH becomes more severe, TDH attempts to compensate this situation. Therefore, it could be the body's attempt to correct the oxidative stress caused by DDH.

The fact that the male-female ratio of control group patients is not statistically the same can be seen as a limitation. Due to the high female predominance in DDH, we could not achieve the same rate in the control group. Instead of DDH patients with different severities and different treatment methods, similar patient profiles and the same treatment methods may make the study more homogeneous. However, it was observed that the success of the treatment, not the type of treatment, was effective on the results. The strength of this study may be that a high number of DDH patients were analyzed in comparison with the control group prospectively.

Previous studies have reported that DDH is associated with torticollis and metatarsus adductus. In our study, however, none of the 95 patients with DDH had torticollis or metatarsus adductus; further studies are necessary to investigate this information. In the existing literature, the link between pathologies and oxidative stress has been investigated increasingly more frequently. However, although DDH is the most common dysplasia of the musculoskeletal system, there is a scarcity of evidence regarding with specific oxidative stress pathways.

Conclusion

Oxidative stress increases in DDH, but it is not directly related to TDH. Further, in addition to the improvement in oxidative stress parameters, treatment of DDH leads to a positive change in TDH.

Declarations

Conflicts of interest/Competing interests: Authors declare no conflict of interests.

Ethical Approval

The study received local ethics committee approval (decision no: HRU/20.07.16-16987). The families of all participants were informed about the study procedure and provided written informed consent. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical of the standards 1964 World Medical Association's Declaration of Helsinki.

The location of the study

This prospective comparative study was conducted at Harran University Faculty of Medicine, Department of Orthopaedics and Traumatology between April 2020 and May 2023.

Acknowledgments

This study was supported by Harran University Scientific Research Projects (project number: 22208). The authors are grateful for the academic support of Harran University.

Contributions of the Study Group Members

Baki Volkan ÇETİN: Design, Data Collection and Processing, Analysis and Interpretation, Literature Review, Writing, Critical Review

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Mehmet Akif ALTAY: Conception, Design, Supervision

Hakim ÇELİK: Analysis and Interpretation

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All authors approved the final version of the manuscript to be published.

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